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Radioactivity Monitoring in Ocean Ecosystems

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Disclaimer

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RAMONES project's main objective is to close the current marine radioactivity under-sampling gap and foster new interdisciplinary research in ocean ecosystems. RAMONES will invest a significant effort to provide tools to enable long-term data acquisition missions, rapid deployments, low cost per information byte, and propose new AI and Robotics-driven and supported methodologies, being ambitious to eventually offer scaled-up solutions to researchers, policy makers and communities. All these may be achieved by combining state-of-the-art (SoA) methodologies and equipment from various disciplines in a well-balanced synergy, and designing new and effective methodologies targeting the marine environment, which will provide efficient response to existing natural and man-made hazards, and shape future policies for the global population. RAMONES will additionally contribute to shaping a blueprint on Environmental Intelligence in the EU and worldwide.

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
AUG	Autonomous Underwater Glider
α SPECT	Underwater Alpha Spectrometer
CHERI	Cherenkov Imager
CTD	Conductivity, Temperature and Pressure Sensor
CZT	Cadmium Zinc Telluride
EviNS	Evologics Intelligent Networking Software
GASPAR	Gamma Spectrometer for Marine Radioactivity Studies
GPS	Global Positioning System
HPGe	High-Purity Germanium
MCA	Multi-channel Analyzer
NIM	Nuclear Instrument Module
SoA	State of the Art
SUGI	Submarine Gamma Imager
USBL	Ultrashort Baseline

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Abstract

RAMONES offers a new fleet of instruments to perform continuous and in situ measurements of natural and artificial radioactivity in the marine environment as part of the main objectives. Those instruments will be developed, optimized, validated and deployed in the field based on implementing specific functional characteristics, optimizing integrated solutions, and fine-tuning their overall architecture.

The main effort in RAMONES is to define the new state-of-the-art in radioactivity monitoring in ocean ecosystems investing in innovative stationary and mobile platforms. Light-weight, high-resolution, power-efficient solutions will be sought for radiation spectrometers integrated aboard autonomous underwater vehicles (gliders). A benthic laboratory is currently developed as a multi-instrument platform to offer high-resolution spectroscopy and imaging capabilities coupled with additional sensors. An autonomous surface vehicle will bridge the communications between the underwater vehicles and instruments. That way, cross communication among instruments and remote stations will be ensured by investing in efficient, high-transmission rate, low-power communication instruments to facilitate the coordinated monitoring by both the mobile and stationary platforms.

This report provides an overview of the latest development tests and the preparation for the field operations in Milos and Kolumbo hydrothermal fields. This includes a survey of background information and data from related projects about the target sites, logistics, and relevant operation permissions.

1. Introduction

1.1. Context

This report is deliverable D3.1 “Development tests and field operations preparation” of the H2020 FET PROACTIVE RAMONES project. The report is a product of the tests performed on all tasks of WP1 and WP2, as well as the preparation work for field experiments as defined in WP3 “Onsite Integration, Testing and Pilot Demonstrators”.

1.2. Contents and Rationale

The main purpose of the document is to present the tests carried out for the instruments that are currently being developed, either in the lab or in the field, as well as the background information collection and preparation for the main project campaigns in hydrothermal fields of Milos Island and Kolumbo underwater volcano.

Section 2 of the document shares information with the following three deliverables due to the iterative nature of instruments’ development and testing, including any new testing procedures and results:

D1.3 - 2nd Instrument release and laboratory testing

D2.2 - Report on systems integration and validation

D4.1 - Report on preprocessing and calibration software development

Section 3 is splitted between the Milos and Kolumbo field work preparations. For each test site, it provides the background information that has been collected and processed by partners from previous projects, suggested points of interest for RAMONES instruments deployments, provisioned logistics and permissions, as well as preliminary field operations plan and expected results.

2. RAMONES instruments development testing procedures and results

This section reports on the current testing status for each of the RAMONES instruments and vehicles.

2.1. SIMBLA - SIMulations of detectors and development of the Benthic Laboratory (T1.2)

Simulations of γ -Sniffers have been completed prior to laboratory and field tests, as reported in D1.2. Simulations are an important part of the optimization and validation of radiation sensors and may be revisited.

2.2. Benthic Laboratory

The stationary benthic laboratory platform will host the radioactivity detectors and imaging instruments at the sea bottom for long-term, high-resolution measurements. Moreover, it will serve as a data relay point and positioning aid for the autonomous underwater gliders (AUGs). The development of the benthic laboratory platform has been started and advancements have been made in the control unit (hardware and software) including sensor connectivity and the energy subsystem.

Figure 1. Control unit prototype internals connected with γ -Sniffer

The Benthic Labs control unit is the heart of the platform. It is based on a low power single board computer (SBC) and includes all the related electronic modules for instrument connectivity, communications control, data management and logging, power cycling scheduling and management to reduce overall energy consumption and increase platform autonomy. A prototype control unit has been developed and has been tested already with

the available RAMONES instruments (γ -Sniffer, SUGI, CHERI UV camera, and CTD) in the lab and it will be tested in the sea in the forthcoming Milos field experiment. The testing included both hardware connectivity and software control and after some troubleshooting, it performed as expected.

2.3. GASPAR - Gamma Spectrometer for Marine Radioactivity Studies (T1.3)

No testing to report at this time due to late procurement (still pending).

2.4. γ -Sniffers (T1.4)

During routine measurements with one of the μ Spec4000 detectors (S/N: 0277) an abnormality was observed. The measured spectrum of a bentonite sample, known to contain the daughter products of the uranium and thorium decay chains appeared only partially, up to ~ 2230 keV. This is more accentuated by the fact that the ^{208}Tl line at 2614.511 keV, clearly measured by a HPGe detector, was not present in the spectrum obtained by the μ Spec.

Figure 2. Comparative spectra of the same bentonite sample. While the HPGe detector exhibits a detection range of 0-3 MeV, the μ Spec appears to be somehow limited to 0-2.2 MeV. See text for more details.

After verifying the same observation with the ^{208}Tl line, and the respective energy range, with other natural samples, a call was made between partners to examine if this limitation was present with the other detectors (S/N: 0278, 279). Both remotely, and in person, a similar observation was made. Therefore, towards optimal detector functionality, we contacted the manufacturer who suggested a series of tests. The tests resulted in sending the detectors back to the manufacturer and upon return they were fully functional with the energy range corresponding to the desired specifications.

Two γ -Sniffer prototypes have been integrated and tested with the Benthic Lab control unit and a ROV and are ready to be integrated into the gliders.

Before the first field tests, an underwater measurement was performed in the lab. Two different CZT detectors (μ SPEC4000 and GR1) were encapsulated inside a plastic housing and submerged into a plastic container filled with tap water. ^{40}K is a common natural radioisotope found in the marine environment thus it is essential to investigate the detectors' response for this specific isotope. For that reason, a fertilizer known to have ^{40}K content was diluted into the water to create a homogeneous ^{40}K volume source.

On the following graph, a comparison between the count rates registered from both detectors during the measurements described above is presented. Any differences are mainly due to the difference in the dimensions of the CZT crystal.

Figure 3. Measurement setup (left) and comparison of the count rate registered from both detectors (right).

2.5. SUGI - Submarine Gamma Imager (T1.5)

The SUGI instrument provides gamma imaging capabilities. The GDS-100 system from IDEAS has been selected as the main module, which comprises four GDS-10 detector submodules, each with 121+2 channels, for accommodating the 11 \times 11 pixelated CZT (anode) and the cathode signals. Extensive effort has been dedicated into building a comprehensive Python library which offers all the functionality required to operate the GDS-100 system through the provided TCP/IP interface, based on the specifications of the data packets provided by the manufacturer. During the development phase, the various features of SUGI and the GDS-100 system have been tested in the lab based on background radiation. The tests consisted mainly of the comparison of the analytics on the collected data produced by the proprietary software of the manufacturer and the developed SUGI API, as well as comparisons between

measurements collected simultaneously by SUGI and the gSniffers. During the development, some bugs have been identified and some new features were requested for the GDS-100 system, which have been accommodated by the manufacturer in corresponding firmware updates.

Figure 4. Testing SUGI integration with Benthic Lab.

Figure 5. First water tests of SUGI and γ -Sniffer in the lab's pool.

2.6. α SPECT - Underwater Alpha Spectrometer (T1.6)

- Analyzer module

The design of the alpha spectrometer α SPECT has been finalized to the most of its details. A PV detector module has been tested for operational capability in laboratory conditions using standard NIM modules. In particular, the PV module was tested for bias supply stability and signal connectivity. Further development and testing are required once the gas membrane and respective gas chamber (under design) is complete. An MCA module has been acquired and is individually tested (see some screenshots in the figure below).

Figure 6. Testing of the PV module for α SPECT

- Gas separation and conditional module

A system for extracting radon gas from high pressure water has been designed and currently is under components procurement for building an initial prototype. For this reason, there is no testing to report in this period, however there are a number of development tests planned for the coming months.

The first will be to test different membrane materials for their permeability for different gases. The tests will be done in a specialized pressure chamber for simulating the deep-water pressure and combined with a mass spectrometer for accurate quantifying.

Testing the internal environmental sensors (CO₂, humidity, temperature, etc) is not expected to produce any surprises as they have been well understood and robust for decades now.

Special attention will be paid in the development and testing of the vacuum control valves and pump for handling the high differential pressures that can exist while system operation.

2.7. CHERI - Cherenkov Imager (T1.7)

CHERI imager consists of two individual instruments; one single photon camera optimized for ultra-low light imaging, and one high bandwidth camera optimized in near UV spectrum.

For the solution based on the single photon camera, the suitability of the sensing device and initial tests have been performed using a sample product kindly provided by the manufacturer (Micro Photon Devices) for demonstration purposes. The results of these initial tests have been reported in D4.1. Besides the test with the demo device, there is no testing to report for the single photon camera at this time due to late procurement (still pending).

The UV camera has arrived at the end of 2022 at partner PLOA after a year from the order due to the global chips shortage. Some initial tests have been performed to test that the device operates correctly. These tests include the acquisition of images using different parameter settings and under different lighting conditions using the proprietary Windows software. We are working on the development of software tools for controlling the camera and acquiring images on a Raspberry Pi 4 platform.

2.8. Cooperative Navigation (T2.1)

Before the consortium had access to RAMONES platforms, preliminary work was done on the development and implementation of selected methods for cooperative navigation and underwater target localization, followed by real tests with the Medusa-class of autonomous marine vehicles that are property of IST-ID. In the context of RAMONES, where only one tracker (the autonomous surface vehicle) will be used, the algorithms can be adapted to allow tracking of the evolution of the underwater gliders, albeit at the cost of maneuvering the surface unit in a specific pattern. Preliminary work on this task is described in Deliverable D2.1 and further results are presented in Deliverable D2.2.

2.9. Adaptive Motion Planning and Cooperative Control (T2.2)

Cooperative control is envisioned to afford the surface and underwater robotic platforms the capability to maneuver in a concerted manner, either following a pre-defined mission plan or generating the plan on-line, over successive time windows, in response to episodic events. In RAMONES work was undertaken to develop and implement selected methods for cooperative control and underwater target localization, followed by real tests with autonomous marine vehicles that are property of IST. On the motion planning front, study of offline cooperative motion planning has led to the development of a software package and an on-line adaptive, or event-driven, alternative is currently under development. Preliminary work on this task is described in D2.1 and further results are presented in Deliverable D2.2.

2.10. Positioning and Communications (T2.3)

Due to their extreme low power requirements and low payload, gliders have rudimentary navigation systems, not compatible with the applications envisioned for RAMONES. To address this issue, a positioning and communication system was developed based on ultra-short baseline acoustic devices. Moreover, to estimate quantities that are not directly measured and to improve the accuracy of the position estimates, preliminary concepts for cooperative navigation were also studied, exploiting inter-vehicle communication links and the use of relative range and/or bearing measuring units among vehicles, which may still be often available even if position fixes are not acquired. The positioning and communications of the RAMONES system are detailed in Deliverable D2.1.

2.11. Software Systems Integration and Validation using HIL Simulations (T2.4)

RAMONES oversaw modifications to the Medusa software stack in order to integrate the Evologics' acoustic modem emulator, the Glider backseat driver, and the ROC-SIANI Saildrone. HIL simulations in combination with the acoustic modem emulator are already possible using IST-ID vehicles. Stand-alone HIL simulations are independently possible with the Saildrone and Glider and these vehicles are in the process of being added to the integrated RAMONES system. A description of the complete RAMONES system software and details on individual nodes, simulations, and experiments are reported in Deliverable D2.2.

2.12. Systems Integration with robotic vehicles (T2.5)

Systems integration tasks include:

- Modification of Slockum glider AUVs. An extra dry payload section required to be added for extending the gliders in order to fit the RAMONES electronics (modems and logging computer).
- Interfacing RAMONES electronics with gliders' navigation system.
- Installation of USBL / modem transducers and gSniffer.

Modifications designs have been almost completed and the glider payload sections are under procurement status. Field tests will be performed soon after the receiving of the payload extension sections and the integration of the RAMONES systems.

Initial experimental tests with the glider vehicles at the surface proved to be a success. Hardware adaptations had to be performed to allow testing of the glider's control and navigation at the surface. These entailed a contraption providing additional flotation and additional ballast, as well as a rudder extender to increase the vehicle's maneuverability, resulting in a reduction of the minimum turning radius by 59% (figure 6). The radio link worked all the time for the whole extent of the dock and the GPS was able to get fixes during all trials at the surface. The vehicle was able to achieve a speed of 0.70 m/s and could turn a radius of 15 m with the rudder extender installed and more than 30 m without. To minimize the tendency to turn right, adjustable trim tabs were designed and will be installed at a fixed angle of -5 degrees with a mobile component that can be adjusted +/- 10 degrees for fine-tuning.

Further details on the glider development and the integrated RAMONES system of all assets and their respective software components are available in Deliverable D2.2 – Report on Systems Integration and Validation.

Figure 7. Initial testing with the glider.

3. Test sites field operations preparations

This section reports all the field operations preparation up to M27. It includes background information and data from target sites (Milos Island, Kolumbo underwater volcano) that has been collected and analyzed by partners from previous projects, in order to prepare the surveys and optimize the characterization at each site.

This task also identifies specific sites for testing, logistics (transportations, lodgings, support ships, etc), as well as survey and operation permissions that may be needed from local authorities.

3.1. Milos island hydrothermal field site

- Background

Milos is the south-western edge of the Cyclades islands in the Aegean Sea, Greece, and the largest island of Milos volcanic complex. It is located at the NW part of the modern active Aegean Volcanic Arc, an area characterized by intense volcano-tectonic activity. Volcanism in Milos initiated 3.5 mys ago, covering almost the entire island with volcanic products and continued up to 80 thousand years ago.

The neotectonic configuration of Milos is complex, with uplifting or subsiding blocks and even tilting or rotations around inclined axes. The most dominant tectonic features, which have configured the overall morphology of the island, are two major fault zones bounding the central block of Milos – Fyriplaka tectonic graben (MFTG).

Faults bounding the fault blocks of the island have served as conduits for geothermal fluids resulting in alterations of the adjacent volcano-sedimentary formations, giving rise to a spectrum of exploitable industrial mineral and hydrothermal deposit types on-land, and exploited since the antiquity.

These hydrothermal manifestations do occur also underwater, extending from the shore to depths of 500 m or more, although the submarine hydrothermal system around the island is not fully mapped. Thus, today Milos constitutes a preserved onshore and offshore laboratory to study hydrothermal processes. In the near-shore environment, the most intense hydrothermal venting activity (0–15 m water depth) is located along the SE coastline at Paleochori Bay corresponding with the prolongation of the eastern marginal fault of the Milos – Fyriplaka neotectonic graben, which hosts the Firiplaka subaerial volcano.

Here the distribution of hydrothermal outflow, temperatures of the seafloor, and association with bacterial and other microbial communities has been studied in recent times by members of Ramones Project, and thus provides a natural laboratory to a) evaluate the levels of natural radioactivity both associated with the hydrothermal outflow underwater, and away from it,

and b) test instrumentation and evaluate deployment techniques adapted for environmental monitoring underwater.

- Relevant data

Figure 8. Geodynamic position of Milos within the Hellenic Volcanic Arc (After Nomikou et al., 2013.)

Figure 9. Map showing the neotectonic configuration of Milos (After Papanikolaou et al., 1990).

Figure 10. Paleochori Bay showing the approximate bathymetric contours, overlain on satellite imagery showing areas of hydrothermal outflow at the seafloor (white areas).

Figure 11. Close-up of a zone of hydrothermal activity at paleochori Bay, showing a polygonal pattern of hydrothermal outflow, as indicated by white areas that correspond to bacterial mats. These areas are also associated with degassing, with gas bubbles (mainly

Figure 12. Areas at Paleochori Bay that are accessible at shallow water <2 m) in ellipses. Larger patches at ~10 m water depth

Figure 13. Detail of drone photomosaic showing the near-shore patches of bacterial mats (white) associated with both fluid flow and degassing at Paleochori.

- Field ops sites

Figure 14. Zones of degassing around Milos Island. Land-based degassing provides a point of comparison (intensity, tectonic controls, radioactive signal) to compare with and extrapolate to the underwater systems. Milos also shows numerous areas of underwater hydro

Figure 15. Zones of hydrothermal outflow near and around Paleochori Bay (Easter Bay in this image)

In the following table are the points of interest that will be used for collecting data for background radioactivity estimation.

Sites	GPS Coordinates		Description	Duration (h)	Dates
Paleochori beach	36°40'29.19"N	24°30'56.63"E	Near Sirocco hotel, 0,2 and 4 meters	4	to be scheduled
Paleochori secret beach	36°40'25.73"N	24°30'45.97"E	0, 2 and 4 meters	4	March 26
Agia Kiriaki beach	36°40'3.91"N	24°29'46.22"E	0, 2 and 4 meters	4	to be scheduled
Kalamos Volcano fumaroles	36°40'9.11"N	24°29'31.05"E	on shore, near agia Kiriaki beach	2	to be scheduled
Seep C1	36°40'15.07"N	24°30'15.20"E	on shore, near agia Kiriaki beach		to be scheduled
Voudia beach	36°44'33.86"N	24°31'53.93"E	unknown sites, to be tested	4	to be scheduled
Thiorychia sulfur mine beach	36°41'38.64"N	24°32'41.53"E	to be tested	4	to be scheduled
Thiorychia sulfur mine	36°41'47.38"N	24°31'51.86"E	to be tested		to be scheduled
Alykes power station	36°42'21.24"N	24°28'13.24"E	0, 2 meters depth	4	March 25
French military cemetery	36°43'17.72"N	24°26'19.21"E	to be tested	4	to be scheduled
Phare Adamas	36°43'12.43"N	24°26'6.69"E	to be tested	4	to be scheduled
Seep C2	36°43'58.65"N	24°26'33.68"E	on shore near Adamas	3	to be scheduled
Seep C3	36°43'52.61"N	24°26'53.52"E	on shore near Adamas		March 25

- Campaign preparation (March 2023)

The purpose of this campaign is two-folded. First, it will provide field time for testing the currently developed instruments with realistic scenarios in easily accessible sites (water depths to ~10 m). Second, it will provide ground truth data from realistic case scenarios that will be used to validate instruments performance and develop surveying, monitoring, and modeling techniques.

Main goal is to establish the levels of activity, to determine if sensors are sensitive for a full-fledged deployment that is useful for monitoring of a natural system, or if technology needs development to decrease detection levels, and/or to adapt the strategy of monitoring.

The experiments will help addressing the following open questions/issues:

- Characterize radioactivity levels and radionuclides (both in situ or at lab) in:
 - a) sediment
 - b) water
 - c) complemented with land-based measurements
- Quantify unknown parameters:
 - Detection level of instruments
 - ❖ Which signals of interest can be measured
 - ❖ What is the minimum integration time for detecting them
 - ❖ Which are the proper settings
 - ❖ Which signal thresholds will be used as indicators
 - ❖ Based on integration times: glider flight strategy or fix point monitoring (longer integration times)

- Reconnaissance of field area for future instrument deployments (activity vs. sensitivity of instruments). Is Milos (and this Paleochori bay) suitable for RAMONES demonstration pilots with gliders (e.g., measure steadily increased radioactivity as the gliders approach the coastline)?
- Compare measurement subaerially.
- Structural characterization of instrumented seeps:
 - ❖ Type of structures (e.g. faults, fractures, fractured corridor)
 - ❖ Structural attributes (e.g. strike, dip, length, aperture)
 - ❖ Structural location (e.g. in relation to the fault, to the graben)
 - ❖ Relations with the aquifer, the volcanic center, the regional tectonics
- Signature of natural systems (sources, mixing, etc)
 - ❖ sampling locally (vents vs. outside vents)
 - ❖ sampling regionally -> zones w/ venting vs. no venting

Overall, the plan is to test RAMONES instruments (gSniffers, SUGI, CHERI UV) in a real environment for helping address the above questions and estimating/measuring background radiation levels (with standard sampling) in a known active vent field area for correlating it with RAMONES instruments.

To meet the above objectives, several meetings have been held and a Field Ops Preparation Document has been developed that sets the guideline and planning for this campaign. A copy of the document is in Appendix 1.

3.2. Kolumbo underwater volcano

- Background

Shallow submarine volcanoes such as Kolumbo have complex geology and the investigation of their hydrothermal systems is still at an early stage. These shallow underwater, high-energy, dynamic hydrothermal systems are associated with significant and potentially hazardous volcanic activity.

Kolumbo submarine volcano is located just 7 km from the well-known Santorini volcanic islands. It is the most active submarine volcano in the Mediterranean Sea and in 1650 AD, it erupted explosively resulting in approximately 70 fatalities from toxic gasses on nearby Santorini and significant coastal damage from tsunamis. It is considered a submarine volcanic environment with high probability for magmatic and tectonic activities, and consequent

natural hazards (lava flows to tephra flows, pyroclastic flows, landslides, magmatic degassing, hydrothermal eruptions with potential release of toxic metals, earthquakes, tsunamis). Its proximity to Santorini underlines the critical importance of raising public awareness concerning a potential hazard, in terms of at least the local population.

The shallow crater of Kolumbo (<500 m depth) currently hosts a hydrothermal field with active and inactive sulfide-sulfate hydrothermal chimneys and mounds that are metalliferous. It constitutes an extreme environment with vertical inner crater walls, high temperature hydrothermal vent field, CO₂ degassing and acidic conditions within the crater, unstructured natural obstacles and poses a potential ocean acidification hazard as a result of the build-up of hydrothermally emitted CO₂ in the crater. Around the submarine volcano sulfide-sulfate hydrothermal chimneys and mounds at 500m depth, provide habitats for microorganisms that are not found or that are only detectable in very low numbers in other marine habitats within an active vent field.

Thus, Kolumbo serves as a unique natural laboratory for interdisciplinary studies due to: (i) its accessible location, (ii) the variety of potential natural hazards, (iii) extreme environmental gradients, (iv) localized ocean acidification, (v) unique hydrothermal mineralization and associated ecosystems and (vi) the urgent need to assess hazards to nearby populations.

At present, critically active shallow submarine volcanoes near highly populated areas (such as Kolumbo) are only monitored sporadically. SANTORY, an ongoing related project, addresses this deficiency by establishing a first-of-its-kind comprehensive seafloor observatory using autonomous instruments to monitor key parameters of hydrothermal and volcanic/seismic activity (e.g. temperature, seafloor deformation and CO₂ degassing) and for the first time ever establish reference monitoring protocols in the sense of combining active volcano measurements with Santorini's on-land data (e.g. seismic, geodetic, geochemical), thus providing the necessary impetus for developing novel risk assessment mechanisms.

- Relevant data

Figure 16. 3D Bathymetric map of Kolumbo volcano (Nomikou et al., 2022).

Figure 17. ROV photo from the active hydrothermal vent field of Kolumbo.

- Field ops sites

Figure 18. High resolution swath map with the locations of SANTORY instruments within Kolumbo crater.

- Cruise participation (December 2022)

The installation of innovative marine technology machinery in the active underwater volcano of Kolumbo, NE of Santorini, was successfully completed by the international scientific team of the **SANTORY** research program "**SANTORini's seafloor volcanic observatorY**", an ongoing related project, which is funded by the Hellenic Foundation for Research and Innovation (HFRI) and coordinated by the Laboratory of Physical Geography of NKUA (www.santory.gr).

For the first time in the Eastern Mediterranean Sea, a shallow (at 500m depth) underwater volcanic observatory (SANTORY) is being established within the Kolumbo crater, with the use of research vessel Filia and the Underwater Unmanned Vehicle Max Rover, owned by the Hellenic Centre for Marine Research (HCMR).

The underwater observatory contains sensors that measure the physical and chemical parameters of the active hydrothermal field of Kolumbo, while special thermometers were placed at specific points to measure the high temperature of the field (230°C) and inclinometers on the floor of the crater. A visual recording of the active part of the chimneys was conducted and their morphology was compared to data collected in previous oceanographic expeditions. In addition, during the oceanographic expedition, different kinds of material were collected a) from the water column using special Niskin-type samplers, b) from the microbial mat covering the crater floor and c) from the sediments of the hydrothermal field with the submersible vehicle Max Rover. Samples from the active metal-rich chimneys of Kolumbo were also collected in order to perform new geochemical analyses. In the next year, additional scientific instruments will be prepared and installed by the project partners.

SANTORY will develop and use innovative marine technologies that will not only broaden our knowledge of the dynamics and dangers of hydrothermal fields, providing free data to both the scientific community and society, but also lead to the creation of a model system for the development of underwater observatories worldwide.

SANTORY, relevance of RAMONES, will map the natural radioactivity field above the hydrothermal vents of Kolumbo and track the outflow fluids based on crust-generated radon activity measurements. Additionally, we will fuse the physical, chemical and γ -radiation data recorded above the vent field and the geodetic data and register them to the 3D topography and the seabed mapping. For this reason, 3 members from RAMONES were participating on this cruise: Evi Nomikou (NKUA and SANTORY PI), Angelos Mallios (PLOA), and Christos Antoniou (NTUA).

Figure 19. An underwater observatory which contains sensors that measure the physical and chemical parameters of the active hydrothermal field of Kolumbo.

4. Conclusions – Future Steps

Paleochori Bay in Milos provides an ideal field test area of instrumentation: it is accessible, and the hydrothermal manifestations are accessible both onland and in shallow water, there is sufficient background information to correlate field data acquired in the past with measurements within the RAMONES project (both natural samples and instrumental data), and the area is a site of continued interest that will provide further context in the future. RAMONES data, once the instrumentation is validated and tested, will also provide valuable information to understand the geological processes there, and the evaluation of fluxes associated with both fluid and gas hydrothermal outflow. These tests at Milos are also key to develop monitoring strategies that are applicable to other environments, such as Kolumbo volcano, and open the door to the development of sensors for deeper water deployments.

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- Appendix 1

RAMONES field work preparation document

25 March - 1 April 2023

[Mylos island vent field](#), Greece

List of Participants

Person	Partner	Date in	Date out
AUGER, Sylvain	U Lyon	27/3/2023	3/4/2023
GRANDJEAN, Philippe	U Lyon	27/3/2023	3/4/2023
MARTELAT, Jean Emmanuel	U Lyon	27/3/2023	3/4/2023
CAVAILLHES, Thibaut	U. Bordeaux	27/3/2023	31/03/2023
BEJELOU, Konstantina	NKU Athens	25/3/2023	1/4/2023
MERTZIMEKIS, Theodoros	NKU Athens	24/3/2023	30/3/2023
MADESIS, Ioannis	NKU Athens	26/3/2023	30/3/2023
SILTZOVALIS, Georgios	NKU Athens	24/3/2023	27/03/2023
NOMIKOU Evi with Eirini Anagnostou	NKU Athens	27/3/2023	30/3/2023
BRETON, Vincent	UCA/LPC	25/3/2023	31/03/2023
CHARDON, Patrick	UCA/LPC	25/3/2023	31/03/2023
TERRAY, Luca	UCA/LPC	25/3/2023	31/03/2023
MAIGNE, Lydia	UCA/LPC	25/3/2023	31/03/2023
MALLIOS Angelos	PLOA	24/3/2023	30/3/2023

Vlasopoulos Othonas	PLOA	24/3/2023	30/3/2023
CABECINHAS, David	IST-ID	24/3/2023	31/3/2023
NIKOLOPOULOS Konstantinos (Kostas)	UDUR	28/03/2023	29/03/2023
KARANZALOS Konstantinos	NTUA	24/3/2023	28/3/2023
NTOUSKOS Makis	NTUA	24/3/2023	30/3/2023
ANTONIOU Christos	NTUA	24/3/2023	30/3/2023
SPANOS Sotiris	NTUA	24/3/2023	30/3/2023

Instruments

Instrument	Specs	Partner
gSniffer x3	Depth rating 500 m. 1x Cable 10 m long (connected to laptop on surface) 1x Attachable to ROV (logging through tether) 1x cable 6 m long (connected to laptop)	PLOA NTUA NKUA
SUGI radioactivity imaging	Depth rating 500 m ROV deployment	NTUA / PLOA
CHERI UV imaging	(to be confirmed early March) Depth rating 500 m ROV deployment	PLOA / NTUA
ROV "METIS"	Depth rating 500 m 1 km fiber optic tether	NTUA
RadonEye	Subaerial measurements	PLOA
Thermal camera	Handheld	PLOA

CTD	Stand alone or ROV connected	PLOA
1 AlphaGuard	Near real-time water sample measurements	UCA
2 RadonEye	Subaerial measurements	UCA
1 Colibri		UCA
1 radiagem	Subaerial measurements	UCA
1 thermal camera		UCA
1 GoPro camera	Pictures and videos (till 10 m depth)	UCA
Sampling material	water, sediments, gas? Sediments, water, misc	UCA NKUA
Aerial drone	Optical mosaicing (shallow water, land) Thermal imaging	ULyon
AMESOS	Portable in situ spectrometer/dosimeter	NKUA

Scope and goals

The scope of this document is to help prepare and organize the field work, as well as, to prepare experiments checklists.

Main goal is to establish the levels of activity, to determine if sensors are sensitive for a full-fledged deployment that is useful for monitoring of a natural system, or if technology needs development to decrease detection levels, and/or to adapt the strategy of monitoring.

The experiments should help address the following open questions/issues:

- Characterize radioactivity levels and radionuclides (both in situ or at lab) in:
 - a) sediment
 - b) water
 - c) complemented with land-based measurements

→ Quantify unknown parameters:

Detection level of instruments

- ❖ Which signals of interest can be measured
- ❖ What is the minimum integration time for detecting them
- ❖ Which are the proper settings
- ❖ Which signal thresholds will be used as indicators
- ❖ Based on integration times: glider flight strategy or fix point monitoring (longer integration times)

Structural characterization of instrumented seeps :

Type of structures (e.g. faults, fractures, fractured corridor)

Structural attributes (e.g. strike, dip, length, aperture)

Structural location (e.g. in relation to the fault, to the graben)

Relations with the aquifer, the volcanic center, the regional tectonics

Signature of natural systems (sources, mixing, etc)

- ❖ sampling locally (vents vs. outside vents)
- ❖ sampling regionally -> zones w/ venting vs. no venting

→ Reconnaissance of field area for future instrument deployments (activity vs. sensitivity of instruments). Is Milos (and this Paleochori bay) suitable for RAMONES demonstration pilot with gliders (e.g., measure steadily increased radioactivity as the gliders approach the coastline)?

→ Compare measurement subaerially

Moreover, this field work should provide information for addressing the following reviewers' comments:

- Establish natural radioactivity levels (quantify) for the first time in Milos (beach, coastline, water, vents). To elaborate: Milos beaches will be measured for natural radioactivity levels using both a portable spectrometer (AMESOS) and a pre-characterized at the NKUA lab GR1 CZT crystal (not γ Sniffer), side-by-side to establish comparisons. Sand samples will be collected from those sites and measured at a high-res gamma spectrometer at NKUA. For the continental coastline, we will act similarly, if the conditions avail (waves, rain, etc). Shallow depth measurements need to be performed with a gSniffer to establish the interface changes as one moves from land

to water. Sediments will also be collected and measured along the coast line at several locations

- Fully characterize γ Sniffers response under realistic conditions (thresholds, integrations times, counting rates). To elaborate: the results will be evaluated quickly in situ, but further analysis will take place post-experiments after the field tests.
- Benchmark spectrometers with lab-based and in situ measurements using other instruments.
- Establish a firm knowledge of limitations inside the housing material during operation in the water. All of the above are expected to answer the reviewer's comments. Minimum Detection Activities (an important point raised by the reviewers) are extracted by specific methodology in the lab. Once we have the sediments cross validated with high resolution, we will have a definite answer.

Overall, the plan is to test RAMONES instruments (gSniffers, SUGI, CHERI UV) in a real environment for helping address the above questions and estimating/measuring background radiation levels (with standard sampling) in a known active vent field area for correlating it with RAMONES instruments.

- **Main objectives**

1. Conduct a "scout survey" - conduct the necessary data acquisition and processing with gSniffers in order to check if this location is viable for performing trials with the gliders + surface vehicle, at a later stage, in the scope of technology development undergoing in the RAMONES project. Ideally, with the results of this scout survey, we shall be able to define a "search area" which includes (at least) one "strong" vent field for testing purposes. Later on, in a follow-up field test, we shall deploy the vehicles in that area, without giving the location of the vent field (giving only the bounding box which defines the search area) and at the end of the survey we should be able to get a map and the location of highest probability for the vent field "centroid".

In order to address this objective we will perform the experiments described in this document ["gSniffers trials - scout survey detailed plan"](#)

2. Assess gSniffer performance in real conditions, configuration parameters and other factors in order to Decide on the optimal configuration/ settings/ parameters when they are installed on board the platform.

In order to address this objective we will perform the following experiments:

- Test operational capacity of γ Sniffers on land (bias, calibration, short test measurements). Test supporting instruments (Acquisition S/W etc)

- Perform background measurements on the beach, near the wave front and in selected locations with other portable gamma spectrometers
- Perform submarine measurements with γ Sniffers for medium-long time intervals at shallow depths
- Perform submarine measurements with γ Sniffers with consecutive, short-interval measurements at shallow depths (batch process?)
- Perform submarine measurements with γ Sniffers with consecutive, short-interval measurements at normal depths (batch process?), limited only by the length cable. One or two long measurements over the hydrothermal vent field locations (as suggested by Javier's map)
- ROV-based γ Sniffer measurements.??

The above measurements assume (virtually) static positioning of the γ Sniffer. An additional set of measurements should be performed to check approach to /departure from the vent location:

- Perform submarine measurements with γ Sniffers with consecutive, short-interval measurements (batch process?), as slow as possible speed (either by hand or ROV). A few tests with additional speeds (e.g. 20 cm/s 50 cm/s 100 cm/s) should be performed, too. This depends on the availability of ROV or boat/canoe
- Number of measurements depends on how many γ Sniffers will be ready for deployment (3)
- NOTE: Many of the measurements depend on weather conditions

3. Measure background radiation level

4. Is - make measurements away from the vent field. Measure both in Paleochori Bay (site of hydrothermal activity that is documented and mapped) and in an area with no apparent activity.

In order to address this objective, we will perform the following experiments:

- Perform submarine measurements with γ Sniffers in nearby waters (other locations) with known absence of vent activity. If possible, the detector should be surrounded by a water sphere of radius ~ 1.5 m (check seawater background levels)
- Perform submarine measurements with γ Sniffers in nearby waters (other locations) at shallow depths or placed near the seabed (check sediment background levels).

5. Collect in a systematic way (WP5 kostas.nikolopoulos@durham.ac.uk) all acquired data and initiate WP5 database so all partners have access to the acquired datasets.

Area of work

(maps, points of interest, suggested points of sampling/testing)

Milos - Google Earth -> use time machine to select 12/2011

Figure 20. Paleochori rough bathymetry overlaid with transparency for the hydrothermal activity patches to be visible.

Acoustic data - gas bubbles

Figure 21. Areas accessible at shallow water <2 m) in ellipses. Car access to the beach. Larger patches at ~10 m water depth

Figure 22. Alternative sampling area (Milos internal bay). Has been reported hydrothermal activity but has not been mapped. Optional area also for bad weather.

Experiments

Background (radioactivity) collection/measurement

(description of work, expected outcome, correlation with RAMONES sensors' experiments)

- Regional approach - bays with and without hydrothermal activity - background water composition/activity (after mixing of hydrothermal fluids)
 - Paleochori (mapped hydrothermal activity)
 - Spathi (mapped hydrothermal activity)
 - Bays to the W (no identified activity)
 - Inner bay (reported but unidentified activity)
- Local approach - Measure water/sediment samples relative to hydrothermal vents
 - At ~2 m water depth samples water, sediment at venting areas
 - At ~ 2 m water depth samples water, sediment, away from venting
- Subaerial measurements - Compare instruments and detection levels with marinized and regular instruments
 - Detection efficiency will be determined after relatively long measurements with the different instruments in situ
 - AMESOS γ spectrometer will provide an in situ reference level to compare with
 - Samples (sediments, water) measured with high-res spectroscopy in the lab (post-field test measurements) will provide specific activities to establish the baseline of radioactivity levels

Sites	GPS Coordinates		Description	Duration (h)	Dates
Paleochori beach	36°40'29.19"N	24°30'56.63"E	Near Sirocco hotel, 0,2 and 4 meters	4	to be scheduled
Paleochori secret beach	36°40'25.73"N	24°30'45.97"E	0, 2 and 4 meters	4	March 26
Agia Kiriaki beach	36°40'3.91"N	24°29'46.22"E	0, 2 and 4 meters	4	to be scheduled
Kalamos Volcano fumaroles	36°40'9.11"N	24°29'31.05"E	on shore, near agia Kiriaki beach	2	to be scheduled
Seep C1	36°40'15.07"N	24°30'15.20"E	on shore, near agia Kiriaki beach		to be scheduled
Voudia beach	36°44'33.86"N	24°31'53.93"E	unknown sites, to be tested	4	to be scheduled
Thiorychia sulfur mine beach	36°41'38.64"N	24°32'41.53"E	to be tested	4	to be scheduled
Thiorychia sulfur mine	36°41'47.38"N	24°31'51.86"E	to be tested		to be scheduled
Alykes power station	36°42'21.24"N	24°28'13.24"E	0, 2 meters depth	4	March 25
French military cemetery	36°43'17.72"N	24°26'19.21"E	to be tested	4	to be scheduled
Phare Adamas	36°43'12.43"N	24°26'6.69"E	to be tested	4	to be scheduled
Seep C2	36°43'58.65"N	24°26'33.68"E	on shore near Adamas	3	to be scheduled
Seep C3	36°43'52.61"N	24°26'53.52"E	on shore near Adamas		March 25

Experiments with RAMONES Sensors **γ Sniffers**

Test #	Description	Duration	Expected outcome	Physical Sampling
1	Static over a bubble vent (shallow, if any)	30-60 min per location	Check γ Sniffer response (benthic, ROV, dose rate estimate)	Yes, water and sediments
2	Static over a bubble vent (deep)	30-60 min per location	Check γ Sniffer response (counting rate estimate, to be used for glider thresholds)	Yes, (optional: if there is time and divers are available water, sediments)
3	Static over a bubble vent (deep) at different depths	10 min per distance	Check γ Sniffer response, investigate diffusion/plume (calm sea is required)	Same as in 2
4	Static over a no-activity submarine location, deep	30-60 min per location	Check water sphere background	Same as in 2
5	Static over a no-activity submarine location, shallow	30-60 min per location	Check sediment background levels	Same as in 2
6	Static over a coast location	60 min per location	Check beach sand background levels, establish canvas interpolation	Yes, sediment sand from various locations along the coast line
7	Moving γ Sniffer	Repetitive 10 s, any direction, any depth, any location. Total duration depends on number of points	Establish counting rate, collect spectra under various stats	Not likely

8	Moving γ Sniffer over an already mapped vent region (e.g. “gas bubbles” figure)	Do repeated transects at several depths and speeds. If drone is available record aerial video for visual mapping	Establish if the gamma sniffer can distinguish between “hot” and “cold” areas in a mission and how much is the difference. Gather dataset to be used for glider adaptive guidance.	Not likely
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SUGI

Test #	Description	Duration	Expected outcome
1	Perform on/off tests before deployment, check signals, check response with background, check acquisition	2-3 hours	Operational capability assurance
2	Static over a benthic vent	30% of the time	Operational capability assurance
3	Moving over an extended area	70% of the time	Operational capability assurance

Practical aspects

- [Windy weather forecast](#)
- Minimum support boat we are looking for: inflatable, about 3 m long

- Rough bathymetry KMZ, [local file](#) copied from Navionics website, don't share it outside the RAMONES project.
- [Document shared by Javier Escartin](#) with data from Paliochori bay.
- Local information about [Paliochori bay with nice photos](#)

- PRIOR INFO/DOCS
https://docs.google.com/document/d/1fEiizuhMIBfxaAXEOXCn_aiQfWVhC6RMHxKHZLa65I/edit?usp=sharing
- Milos papers
<https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/11ZADvkA3ICIFMWPxsZzpjT5s8Ys9764G>
- Hotel identified by U Lyon

Capetan Giorgantas <https://capetan-georgantas-hotel-milos-island.hotelmix.fr/>

Meltemi hotel <https://meltemihotelmilos.gr/en/meltemi-milos-hotel/>

Required equipment:

Item(s)	Usage	Partner
Laptops (1 or 2 possibly rugged)	Data logging of gSniffer(s) and SUGI	NTUA
GPS logger	Samples/tests positioning	PLOA
Handheld GPS	Let the boat pilot follow predefined transects	IST
Support boat	Moving γ Sniffer tests	PLOA / NTUA
Other support items: e.g. canopy or umbrellas, chairs/benches, tables, etc.??	Umbrella, portable ice pack cooler(s)	NKUA
Extension power cord & multi-outlet extensions	15m long	NKUA
Power supply (e.g. electric generator, batteries w. Inverters, power banks, etc.)	1 kW inverter for ROV ops (PLOA) Gas generator ? (NTUA)	NTUA / PLOA
Comms (walkie, VHF, UHF, etc)	2x Marine VHF	PLOA
Anchor with release mechanisms	Ropes and weights	NTUA / PLOA
Tapes, small tools, glue gun, office stuff (scissors, paper, pencils, staplers etc), broomsticks		NKUA

Data Storage

- Data storage, handling and circulation among partners and externals are all bound by the DMP (see relevant deliverable and CA)
- Each team responsible for a computer collecting data should make sure they preserve the data integrity and backup. Daily backups are considered a must on portable disks initially and to a remote secure server at a later stage.
- Data will be properly tagged and named. Descriptions are vital for all teams, esp. for all posterior analysis.
- Where possible, geotagging should be recorded.
- Data to be uploaded daily to the common repository ([ELOG Server at NKUA](#))